

Final Report

Project's title:

Strengthening capacities of teachers for the prevention of gender-based violence, Tambograde, Perú.

Prepared by:

Gabriela Salmón
Karina Castañeda
Lucía López
Marixa Bobadilla
Paula Tallman

Gender-based violence (GBV) is one of the most prevalent public health threats in the world today, affecting one in four women in their lifetime (The World Bank, 2019). It is a profound health problem that depletes women's energy, compromises their physical and mental health, and erodes their self-esteem (Rumbidzai C., et al., 2020). The physical and psychological consequences are many, and the literature maintains that in the long term, it could lead to chronic pain, drug and alcohol abuse, and depression among its victims.

In Peru, although national statistics indicate that the evolution of family violence towards women has decreased between 2009 and 2019, it continues to be a major problem in the country. According to the National Observatory of Violence against Women and Members of the Family Group, in Piura, **7 out of 10 women are victims of gender-based violence in their family** (<https://observatorioviolencia.pe/tag/piura/>). Likewise, at the local level, according to statistics from the Ministry of Women and Vulnerable Populations (MIMP), in 2019 the Women's Justice Center (CEM, for the acronym in Spanish) of Tambogrande presented 49 complaints of psychological, physical and sexual violence. It has also been reported that prosecution for sexual abuse have increased in the period 2017-2019 (Municipality of Tambogrande, 2021).

This information has been contrasted with the results of the research called "Water insecurity and gender-based violence: exploring links and steps for prevention. A comparative study of Indonesian and Peruvian women" funded by the British Academy, and implemented in the district of Tambogrande, Piura, between 2020 and 2022.

The study has identified the normalization of GBV in Tambogrande and the stereotypes about gender roles in the home, which perpetuate the cyclical nature of GBV. The results of the study showed that women are in charge of domestic work, care and childrearing, water collection, among other unpaid or recognized tasks. This situation has facilitated long-term impacts such as GBV, teenage pregnancy, increased school dropout among girls and adolescents, and loss of opportunities for women, young people and girls. The local population recognized that one of the main causes of GBV and teenage pregnancy is machismo, religion and gender norms. This leaves women more vulnerable, diminishes their educational opportunities and can lead to early or forced marriages, and prevent or reduce their economic independence.

The results allowed us to identify and recognize that an effective and efficient intervention, proposed by the local stakeholders, was to raise awareness among the population about how this problem was influencing education. Taking this proposal, the Fe y Alegría Rural Network No. 48, located in Malingas-Tambogrande, was contacted to develop **a strategy to strengthen capacities with pre-school teachers on issues of prevention and action against GBV.**

For its implementation, contact was made with an educator from the area with a specialty in curricular design in order to achieve the greatest possible impact. The financing of this activity was obtained through the Academic Directorate of Social Responsibility with the initiative "RSU Fund from the PUCP" 2023 of the Pontificia Universidad Católica del Perú; the call was aimed at the entire university community for the development of University Social Responsibility initiatives. Additional funding was obtained by Willa Poland-McClain, Loyola University student through the CAS Undergraduate Summer Research Experiences program.

DEVELOPMENT OF THE WORKSHOPS

The workshops took place between June 16 and August 25. They included four theoretical-practical sessions.

N° hours	12 hours
Schedule	Friday 2:00 to 5:00 PM
Dates	June 16 and 29, and August 18 and 25, 2023
Closing ceremony	September 8th

The following table presents the contents of the sessions, the learning resources used for their fulfillment, and the hours taught in each topic:

Título del taller	Objetivo	Recurso de aprendizaje	Horas
Workshop 1. Gender approach, an urgent response from the educational curriculum	Know the rates of GBV in girls and adolescents and reflect on the curricular proposal as a response to this problem.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Dynamic: What do we know about the gender approach in national curricular design? • Power Point • Video 	3

Título del taller	Objetivo	Recurso de aprendizaje	Horas
Workshop 2. Identifying sexist practices in early education	Identify sexist practices in the pre-school classroom with the aim of counteracting gender violence.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Participatory dynamics • Power Point • Case study and representation “we identify the types of violence” • Spots on prevention of violence against boys and girls. 	3
Workshop 3. Recognizing myths and realities of early education	Identify the cultural obstacles that have been naturalized in the educational institution to propose strategies that contribute to the deconstruction of these practices that contribute to the construction of the autonomy of girls and boys.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Participatory dynamics “survivors of sexual violence” • Reading: Chapter II of the book “The gender approach, a necessary perspective in the curricular reform of initial and preschool education” • Cooperative work 	3
Workshop 4. Mainstreaming the gender approach in educational practice	Mainstream the gender approach in management documents and learning sessions for the practice of equal opportunity education for boys and girls.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • “Co-responsibility” dynamics • Dynamics “Creating trust” • School’s director team work • Preparation of learning sessions with a gender focus 	3

The workshops had theoretical sessions where statistical information on pregnancy of girls and adolescents in the Piura region, the importance of the gender approach and its mainstreaming in the National Curriculum Design, GBV, types and spaces where it is developed were analyzed. In the last workshop, which was practical, the teaching material used in the sessions was analyzed.

STAFF

The working team from the **Pontificia Universidad Católica (PUCP) del Perú** included Karina Castañeda (sociologist), Lucía López (social communicator), Karen Maldonado (communicator), and Gabriela Salmón (public health specialist) from the Institute of Nature, Earth and Energy. Likewise, the students Valeria Abram Marcos, who attended Tambogrande to be part of workshops 2 and 3, participated as a volunteer, and Willa Poland-McClain who participated in data entry and the preparation of a policy brief.

The workshops were designed and facilitated by **Marixa Bobadilla**, a graduate in education, with a master's degree in pedagogics of educational sciences, with training in gender and public policies and in GBV prevention from school, human rights and citizenship, and sexual education. She has been coordinator of projects on gender and public policies with emphasis on education in the Piura and Cajamarca Region.

The Fe y Alegría Rural Education Program team No. 48 Malingas-Tambogrande contributed to all stages of the training process. They were in charge of the call and monitoring attendance at the workshops, as well as other logistical issues.

RESULTS

Gender concept

According to the surveys administered at the beginning of the workshops, the majority of participants were unaware of the concept of gender.

Some linked it to sex, the differences between masculine and feminine, and as one participant mentioned: "It is the way to identify people's sex." Other interviewees linked it with roles: "It refers to the roles, characteristics of people of both sexes", and others, with the attitudes or abilities of people: "Gender is defined with the attitudes of human beings, both positive and negative" and the characteristics "people, loving, attentive, protective, fighters, entrepreneurs, supportive, concerned, communicative and intelligent leaders." Another group of participants linked it directly to gender inequality. For one of them: "they are the actions that in society often lead us to negative actions towards women." Another related it to equality: "It is the equity between the functions that men and women perform in society."

The workshops allowed these first beliefs to be questioned, and then modified. According to the surveys administered at the end of the workshops, the majority of participants managed to differentiate the concepts of gender and sex. Thus, one participant stated that: "...gender is the group of people with their customs, it is different from sex."

Also, **they linked the concept of gender with the social construction of a person's identity**: "society builds its identity according to actions and stereotypes" and with the characteristics that have been attributed to it in a society: "They are characteristics that are learned in the family or community", "...non-biological characteristics assigned to men and women" and "...the perception of how society sees us." Finally, five respondents defined it considering a binary pattern: "man and woman."

By the end of the workshop, there was still confusion among two respondents with the concept of sex: "a set of human beings of each sex, from a socio-cultural, emotional and biological point of view,"; "It is the perception that society has regarding sex, being defined as masculine and feminine," pointed out the participants.

Perception of gender equality

In both the pre and post workshop surveys, participants mentioned actions as examples of gender inequality identified in the educational environment, at home, at work, and in society. However, through the workshops, they were able to strengthen their knowledge about the difference between biological sex and gender identity, as well as about gender equality: "it was possible to notice that they had little information regarding the transversal axis of gender equality... "They had more information regarding the comments on 'gender ideology' than on the concept of the gender equality approach." according to the facilitator.

On the one hand, they stated that **gender inequality means attributing different roles imposed by society to women and men and promoting certain stereotypes**. For example, women are the only ones in charge of household chores, such as cooking, and men are the ones who must work outside the home: "Prompt the girls to do household things and the men not do household activities (cooking)," indicated one participant. They mentioned that these stereotypes are encouraged from an early age. Comments such as: "...are the use of colors: pink (girl) light blue (boy). Girls are submissive, boys are stronger. Girls use small spaces, and boys use large spaces", evidenced and reinforces a sexist and authoritarian culture.

The above is reflected in concrete actions at home, clearly manifesting the inequalities between men and women, and the **asymmetrical power relations**. "...The man can leave the house with friends when he wants, but the woman cannot, because she belongs to the house" or when "women discriminate against them", "In the way they dress." All of this means that power relations are established, where the decisions of men predominate within a family and can even lead to violence: "Women are very submissive", "it is not easy to defend oneself that easily from a man".

This inequality scales from the domestic to the local, and comments like this confirm it: "they don't let women work in the community." The differences in access to job opportunities and discrimination were also revealed in comments like: "higher ranking jobs such as boss are destined for men", "They do not give women the opportunity to hold political office." "Social isolation" is recognized and that "women are the most discriminated against by society" since there is "inequality when giving an opinion or participation."

RESULTS

The importance of addressing the gender approach in curricular design

“it is necessary to rethink the educational practice from the perspective of gender equality”

Through the workshops, the participants were able to obtain more concrete information linked to gender inequality such as teenage pregnancy in Piura, and they became aware of it. According to the teacher facilitator, they were surprised by the 2022 and 2023 data presented, reacting with indignation. Some of the participants were able to comment on personal experiences and express their emotions more easily, while others preferred to wait for the end of the session to comment on personal experiences.

It was possible to identify the role of education and early education in particular, to incorporate the gender approach from an early age and, as the teacher facilitator pointed out, “lay the foundations on which significant learning will be built, such as contributing to comprehensive development”, “from strengthening the autonomy of boys and girls.” They concluded that “it is necessary to rethink educational practice from a gender equality perspective.”

Another group expressed the **difficulties they go through when talking about gender in schools**. This difficulty may be **due to ignorance and lack of training on the subject from teachers and parents, or due to stereotypes that are reinforced at home and they do not know how to approach the topic**: One of the questions that came up was “how to raise awareness among parents without making them feel offended?”. In many cases, they may fear rejection from society for addressing these issues: “It makes it difficult for me to think of the population or community based on machismo.”

RESULTS

Identifying sexist practices in the classroom

The participants were able to identify the different types of violence and their characteristics. It was possible to open a space for debate and reflection on their notions of violence: “they disagreed on some issues such as “justifying violence” to discipline sons and daughters through violence,” indicated the teacher facilitator of the workshops. Likewise, the debate was opened on the differences in the concepts of man and woman, identified in the Royal Spanish Language Academy.

They managed to identify sexism in classroom management, evidencing “the messages that are provided at pre-school and that perpetuate sexist behaviors” and that “structural violence is present in the manifest and implicit curriculum,” through the learning tools (stories, recreational activities, songs, etc.). One attendee even mentioned: “We were incubating aggressors; and we didn’t know it, what a shame.”

Finally, part of the reflection was to identify the importance of addressing these issues to “see what we sometimes avoid recognizing,” as one participant stated. At the end of the workshop, they managed to make commitments to disseminate the problem in “the different media existing in the communities.”

“*structural violence is present in the manifest and implicit curriculum*”

RESULTS

Deconstructing cultural practices

The participants did not know the routes of care in cases of sexual violence, but they did identify the bureaucratic barriers. They expressed that those were the reasons why the victims gave up filing a complaint: “leading to the re-victimization of the survivor, which mostly leads to giving up the prosecutions.”

A debate was generated around various topics linked to the pre-school stage such as: myths and realities in relation to identities, sexuality, sexual and generic identity, the identities of early and preschool education teachers, children's learning in early and preschool education, considering gender differences, the importance of non-sexist language and games in school learning, and strategies for the equitable development of learning competencies with girls and boys. It was recognized that **within professional teacher training there are myths that translate into barriers**, “thus harming teachers in the extension of the reproductive role due to the fact of being women,” as stated by the teacher facilitator.

RESULTS

Mainstreaming the gender approach in educational management

In the pre-workshop survey, participants expressed the importance of incorporating the gender approach into the regulations of each institution:

"They can be in the construction of rules or laws that can be participatory," but also the importance of implementing them in the classroom: "build agreements in the classroom to reinforce gender equality." They even made proposals for activities that involve fathers and mothers in the learning process, through talks, workshops and awareness strategies, among others: "Offer a parent's school, create 'AWARENESS'." Also, they suggested strategies through work with boys and girls: "Participation of boys in 'girls' things' and vice versa," or using "books with gender equality," among others.

In the workshops, the teachers and principals were able to analyze their Initial Educational Project (PEI), and develop learning sessions for the 3, 4 and 5 year levels.

They proposed areas and achievements of competences incorporating the gender approach. As part of this process, management commitments were also reviewed and adapted. They considered that this exercise has been relevant to translate it into practice in their pedagogical work: "it helps me for self-reflection and bring it into my pedagogical practice".

CONCLUSIONS

In Tambogrande, voices have already been raised denouncing the discrimination to which women are subjected. Their limitations occur at the social, educational, economic and political level, and their contributions are made invisible, which is why awareness about the gender approach and its inclusion as a theme within the contents of educational programs is necessary at all levels of education.

The workshop's experience has reaffirmed the need to incorporate the gender approach in pedagogical practice from the first years of schooling; however, it is necessary to strengthen teachers' capacities first, both at the conceptual and practical level, to implement it successfully. This will allow demystifying concepts and stereotypes and incorporate them properly into learning sessions and educational policies.

The participants expressed the great urgency of addressing this issue, both on a personal level, in the classroom with the students and, above all, with the parents, who often reinforce certain gender stereotypes in the home. The topic of gender approach is a proposal for multi-actor and multi-level intervention. Community organizations, local and regional governments, are fundamental allies to influence the design of differentiated public policies, so promoting and reinforcing this coordination is vital to achieving high-impact objectives.

RECOMMENDATIONS

The recommendations proposed below emanate from the work carried out with the teachers, as well as the suggestions and findings:

1

Continue venturing on similar training processes aimed at including the gender approach in the school curriculum, with other educational levels, both with teachers and principals and with young students.

2

Design workshops with more sessions to reinforce the concepts, and specify the development of the PEI, a fundamental aspect to put it into pedagogical practice.

3

Design specific practical workshops that contribute to eliminating stereotypes in textbooks, reading materials and graphics, exam questions, etc.

4

Extend these concepts and the way of working to incorporate the gender approach in education outside the classrooms to transfer them to the community and especially to parents. As the teachers have suggested and it has also been requested in workshops by various actors in Tambogrande, it is important to reinforce education to prevent violence and the community must be involved. This will also provide transparency and legitimacy to progress in the classroom.

RECOMMENDATIONS

5

Design practical workshops for principals and teachers on topics linked to the legal context of gender equality, so that they can correctly report on the roadmap for possible complaints.

6

Address issues related to violence such as:

- Violence towards women and family
- Violence in the educational environment such as bullying and how to promote tolerance in the classroom, address conflict resolution
- Comprehensive sexual education
- Diversity
- How to address the gender approach and other issues with parents

7

Address other relevant topics in the area such as working with children with different abilities, healthy eating, and managing emotions.

8

Also, the commitment of Fe y Alegría to monitor and give continuance to these learning processes is essential.

Programa de Educación R

Fe y Alegría N° 48

Malingas - Tambogrande

**INTE
PUCP**